

Mitochondria-targeting phosphonium salts of monensin A as the source of novel antiproliferative agents

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ABSTRACT

Monensin A is a representative of natural ionophores, which exhibit a broad spectrum of biological properties, with the most fascinating being its potent anticancer activity. A very intriguing research direction is the rational chemical modification of the monensin A skeleton to obtain analogs with higher antiproliferative activity and selectivity indices. In this paper, synthetic access to monensin A conjugates with mitochondria-targeting chemical moieties, such as the triphenylphosphonium cation and its analogs, is presented. Furthermore, the obtained derivatives were screened for lead structures with improved anticancer properties and mitochondria-targeting ability. Some of the obtained compounds exhibited greater antiproliferative activity and selectivity than unmodified monensin. Furthermore, biological and biophysical studies have confirmed that the induction of apoptosis by the aforementioned hybrids is linked to targeting of mitochondria in cancer cells. These results prove that such a strategy is a promising approach for the search for new effective drug candidates.

1. Introduction

Although many innovative treatment methods have been proposed and a number of new drugs have been introduced, cancer remains one of the main causes of death in the modern world. According to the World Health Organization (WHO) data, in 2020, this disease was responsible for nearly one in six deaths worldwide (almost 10 million deaths) [1,2]. In the same year, 19 million new cases were diagnosed, with the most common types of cancer being that of breast, lung, colon and rectum, prostate, skin, and stomach [2]. Unfortunately, according to WHO forecasts, these values will grow rapidly in the coming years, reaching up to 30 million new cases by 2040 [1]. Considering the above reports, the search for new drugs that would be effective in the fight against different types of cancer is one of the key issues to address in modern science and medicine.

A crucial parameter determining the effectiveness of anticancer drug candidates is selectivity, that is the ability to attack tumors while being neutral towards healthy cells. Designing analogs with a high selectivity index is currently one of the most demanding challenges in cancer therapy. In this context, it is worth mentioning that many diseases

(cancer, diabetes, and neurodegenerative diseases) are related to the functioning of mitochondria [3–5]. These cell organelles have been proven to play an essential role in both extrinsic and intrinsic apoptotic pathways, which makes them significant therapeutic targets for designing new anticancer drugs. Mitochondrial membrane permeabilization is a phenomenon that causes cancer cells to enter the apoptosis pathway and consequently leads to cell death [3–5]. Many substances and chemical groups are known to target mitochondria in cancer cells including rhodamine or pyridinium cations (Fig. 1). The most widely applied is the triphenylphosphonium cation (TPP⁺), which readily accumulates and penetrates the mitochondrial membrane of cancer cells due to its highly negative mitochondrial membrane potential (Fig. 1) [3,5]. Therefore, bioconjugation of the TPP⁺ moiety with other highly bioactive chemical compounds such as ionophore antibiotics may be a source of novel derivatives with potent anticancer properties (Fig. 1).

Monensin A (MON, Fig. 2A) is a natural compound that belongs to the group of polyether ionophore antibiotics (ionophores). It was first isolated in 1967 from *Streptomyces cinnamonensis* and was the first ionophore whose structure has been thoroughly described and explained

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[9]. Like other ionophores, this compound can coordinate metal cations (with the highest selectivity for sodium cation) and transport them across cell membranes, leading to the disruptions in intracellular pH and ion concentration gradients, which in turn results in mitochondrial damage, vacuolization, and cell death (Fig. 2B) [10,11]. This is because of **MON** exhibits strong antimicrobial and anticancer activity. A significant potential of this ionophore in the treatment of cancer has been proven in screening studies aimed at finding potential drugs for prostate cancer. The effects of almost 5000 known drugs and drug-like compounds were examined. Four of them, including **MON**, selectively inhibited the growth of prostate cancer cells at nanomolar concentrations, while showing no significant effect on the growth of healthy prostate epithelial cells [12]. **MON** has also been shown to inhibit cell proliferation in many other types of cancer, including abnormal colon cells, lymphoma, and myeloma, through cell cycle arrest and loss of mitochondrial transmembrane potential [13–15]. Moreover, in recent years, many research groups have carried out chemical modification of **MON**, thus obtaining analogs with high biological activity and promising selectivity indices [16–22]. This indicates that rational modification of the chemical skeleton of **MON** might be an interesting and promising direction in the search for new drug candidates.

Noteworthy, our previous reports indicated that derivatives of another ionophore, salinomycin, obtained by bioconjugation with various TPP⁺ cations via an ester linker, exhibited greater antiproliferative activity towards different cell lines than the lead compound [8]. In addition, physicochemical studies have shown that some of the derivatives exhibit the mitochondria-targeting properties and support the K⁺/H⁺-exchange activity on artificial and natural membranes [8, 23]. Bearing in mind that **MON** exhibits generally higher anticancer activity than salinomycin [16,22], it is expected that its conjugation with various TPP⁺ cations will result in a library of novel analogs showing not only high antiproliferative activity but also the ability to target the mitochondria of cancer cells.

Despite the high anticancer activity of **MON** and its analogs, its primary use as a potential antimicrobial agent should not be ignored. The extraordinary antibacterial activity of **MON** has been confirmed in many studies, and it has also been proven that some of its derivatives (e. g. esters or urethanes) exhibit activity against various Gram-positive bacteria [24–26]. However, many years of ionophore antibiotics usage as veterinary feed additives have increased the problem of drug resistance [27]. Therefore, the search for new ionophore-based compounds that are effective against different types of bacteria is a top-priority task to address. Bioconjugates of biologically active compounds with TPP⁺ have been suggested to exhibit significantly greater antibacterial

properties than starting compounds. Thymol-TPP⁺ conjugates are a perfect example as they showed significantly improved inhibitory activity against Gram-positive bacteria compared to thymol itself [28]. TPP⁺ conjugates with chloramphenicol and various quinone derivatives were also proven to be effective against various types of bacteria [29, 30]. These reports allow us to conclude that conjugates of **MON** with TPP⁺ may also turn out to be potentially effective antibacterial compounds.

2. Results and discussion

2.1. Analogs design and synthesis

As mentioned above, a widely applied method for obtaining mitochondria-targeting compounds is the conjugation of their precursors with the triphenylphosphonium cation (TPP⁺). We decided to expand this idea to include triphenylphosphine derivatives with modified aromatic rings. This approach allows for checking the correlation between the distribution of electron density in the newly introduced substituent and the biological and biophysical properties of the obtained derivatives. In addition, the tributylphosphonium cation was included to assess whether the presence of aromatic rings was necessary to maintain the desired properties. According to our previously published protocol [8], we linked **MON** with TPP⁺ cations at position C1 using an ester bond as a linker. This choice can be justified on biochemical grounds, as the ester bond can be hydrolyzed under physiological conditions due to the presence of esterases in cancer cells [31], which may have a key impact on the biological activity of the obtained analogs. Additionally, the linkers used were chosen to have different carbon chain lengths (four or six carbon atoms) to check whether this property has a direct impact on the ability of the conjugates to enter cancer cells, which corresponds to their biological activity and mitochondria-targeting properties. Taking into account all the above choices, twelve **MON**-TPP⁺ conjugates were synthesized (3a–3f, 5a–5f, Scheme 1). Furthermore, the study also included the benzyl ester of **MON** (6) to assess whether a simple aromatic ester would demonstrate mitochondria-targeting abilities and high biological activity associated with this property.

The desired conjugates were synthesized mainly through a nucleophilic substitution between a halogenated **MON** precursor and the appropriate phosphine (Scheme 1). Starting from **MON**, key ester precursors with terminal bromine atom were obtained according to the protocols published previously with minor modifications [18]. Briefly, **MON** was subjected to esterification reaction with the respective alkyl halide (1,4-dibromobutane or 1,6-dibromohexane) in the presence of

Fig. 1. Typical mitochondria-targeting cations used in medicinal chemistry and ionophore antibiotic conjugates – lasalocid and salinomycin linked to the triphenylphosphonium (TPP⁺) cation – along with their antiproliferative activity [6–8].

DBU, as a non-nucleophilic base, which resulted in the formation of **2** and **4**, with yields of 58 % and 50 %, respectively. The same method was used to synthesize the benzyl ester of **MON** (**6**), using benzyl bromide as the alkyl halide (Scheme 1). The expected product was obtained with a satisfactory yield of 77 %. Having access to halide precursors **2** and **4**, it was possible to obtain the desired conjugates **3a–3f** and **5b–5f** by substitution reactions with appropriate phosphines (Scheme 1). Depending on the length of the linker and the type of phosphine used, the reaction yields ranged from 14 % to 36 %. Surprisingly, this method was unsuitable for obtaining compound **5a**, which is a conjugate of **MON** with triphenylphosphine via a hexane-like linker. This is most likely due to the fact that triphenylphosphine does not have any electron-donating substituents in its structure, which would improve its nucleophilic properties, as in the case of other aromatic phosphines. To address this synthetic problem, a nucleophilic substitution reaction was performed between triphenylphosphine and an excess of 1,6-dibromohexane (to avoid double substitution). This compound was then treated as an alkyl halide and combined with **MON** through an esterification reaction as in previous cases (Scheme 2). The expected product **5a** was obtained with a yield of 43 %.

The purity and structure of the newly synthesized derivatives of **MON** (**3a–3f** and **5a–5f**) were determined using spectroscopic (^1H NMR, ^{13}C NMR, ^{31}P NMR) and spectrometric (HRMS) methods. In the ^{13}C NMR spectra of **MON** derivatives, the signal with the highest analytical significance was assigned to the carbonyl group of the ester moiety at position C1. Depending on the types of substituent and linker used, the signal from the ester group appeared at the narrow range of 176.0–176.3 ppm. In the ^{31}P NMR spectra, the signal from the phosphonium salt appeared in the range of 22.8–34.9 ppm, depending on the type of substituent used. The HRMS analysis confirmed the formation of the desired products, with $[\text{M}]^+$ as the main peak (intensity 100 %). The relative error associated with the analysis was small and ranged from 0.0 ppm to 2.0 ppm, depending on the compound tested. The NMR spectra and HRMS of all the novel **MON** derivatives are included in the Supplementary material (Fig. S1–S48).

2.2. Biological activity

2.2.1. Cytotoxic activity studies

A biological study was conducted to evaluate the cytotoxic activity of **MON** and its derivatives **3a–6** as well as their anti-malignant potential against seven selected cell lines. Cell viability was determined using the MTT colorimetric assay on five cancer cell lines (SW480, SW620, PC3, MDA-MB-231, and A549) and two non-cancerous cell lines (HaCaT and V79). The antiproliferative activity was determined by calculating the

half-maximal inhibitory concentration (IC_{50}). Furthermore, a ratio that measures cytotoxicity in neoplastic and normal cell lines, the selectivity index (SI), was used to measure specificity. Doxorubicin was used as the reference drug in this study.

Compounds **3b**, **3c**, **3d**, **3e**, and **5c** demonstrated significant cytotoxic activity against all tested cancer cell lines, with IC_{50} values $< 1 \mu\text{M}$ (Table 1).

Notably, compounds **3a**, **3c**, and **3d** exhibited more potent anticancer effects towards the PC3 cell line than the conventional anticancer agent, doxorubicin (Table 1). Compounds **3b** and **3c** showed greater anticancer efficacy than **MON** against all tested cancer cell lines, except for A549 (Table 1). The MDA-MB-231 cell line exhibited greater sensitivity to **MON** derivatives, except for compounds **3f** and **6**. Compound **6** had the lowest cytotoxicity, with IC_{50} value approximately 51 times and 16 times higher than those of compound **3d** and **MON**, respectively (Table 1). The selectivity index (SI) was calculated for all selected cancer cell lines in comparison with non-malignant human immortal keratinocyte (HaCaT) and Chinese hamster lung fibroblasts (V79). In the HaCaT cells standard, compound **3a** was classified as highly selective compared to the other derivatives showing SI values < 1 in at least one cell line (Table 2).

Among all derivatives studied, compound **6** showed the most favorable selectivity in SW480 cells (SI = 3.0) and the lowest selectivity in MDA-MB-231 cells (SI = 0.3), indicating that it preferentially targets normal human cells (Table 2). In contrast to HaCaT cells, compound **6** showed lower SI values for V79 cells in all the tested cell lines (Table 2). The huge difference in the SI value of compound **6** in SW480 (SI = 3.0 for HaCaT and SI = 0.3 for V79) may be attributed to the fact that V79 is a non-human cell line. It is worth emphasizing that, as the HaCaT line is of human origin, it should be prioritized in the search for new, effective anticancer agents. Notably, most of the analogs we obtained exhibited higher selectivity index (SI) values than doxorubicin, a drug commonly used in clinical practice – as this compound was highly cytotoxic towards HaCaT cells. Derivates **3a** and **3d** had selectivity index favourable for target cytotoxicity in all investigated cell lines. In the cases of other conjugates the SI varied from very low value to very high, like compound **6** which reaching value of 3.0 for SW480 cell line. It indicates that some derivatives have some specific interactions with particular cancer cell lines. Overall, the **MON** derivatives provide safer and more adequate antineoplastic effects than **MON** alone. Moreover, in most cases, 4-carbon linked conjugates showed greater activity and selectivity than their 6-carbon linked counterparts. Particularly, derivatives **3a** and **3f** not only inhibited the growth of PC3 and A549 cells separately, with low IC_{50} values, but also carried higher SI values, highlighting their prospective therapeutic benefits and potential clinical usage. However,

Fig. 2. (A) Chemical structure of monensin A, (B) Structure of monensin sodium salt.

Scheme 1. Synthesis of MON-TPP⁺ conjugates using various substituents via ester linker.

Scheme 2. Synthesis of the conjugate of MON with triphenylphosphine via a hexane-like linker (5a).

since ionophore antibiotics do not act through a single, well-defined molecular target, the possibility of off-target toxicity should be carefully considered. Therefore, further and more detailed studies of the obtained compounds are necessary to explore their potential anticancer mechanisms beyond those investigated in this work.

2.2.2. Induction of cell cycle arrest

To evaluate the anticancer properties of MON and its derivatives (**3a**, **3f** and **6**), a PI-metric cell cycle analysis was performed using flow cytometry. This method facilitated the identification of cell cycle stage alterations across four phases: sub-G1, G0/G1, S, and G2. A549 and MDA-MB-231 cells were treated with MON and its derivatives (**3a**, **3f**, and **6**) at their respective IC₅₀ concentrations, and incubated for 24 h.

In A549 cells, MON treatment predominantly induced cell cycle arrest in G0/G1 phase (86 % compared to 47.1 % in control) and also significantly reduced the proportion of cells in S phase (from 29.2 % in control to 4.5 %) and G2 phase (from 21.0 % to 6.3 %) (Fig. 3). Compounds **3a** and **3f** demonstrated a similar trend, inducing G0/G1 arrest

in 65.9 % and 63.5 % of cells, respectively (Fig. 3). Additionally, derivative **3a** led to an increase in sub-G1 cells relative to that observed after treatment with MON. In contrast, compound **6** exhibited a cell cycle distribution resembling that of the control group (Fig. 3).

In MDA-MB-231 cells, all tested compounds except derivative **6**, caused G0/G1 phase arrest (ranging from 67.7 % to 69.8 %, compared to 56.7 % in control) and slightly reduced the proportion of cells in S and G2 phases (Fig. 3).

Overall, MON and its derivatives consistently increased the proportion of cells in the G0/G1 phase while reducing the S and G2 phase populations, suggesting that these compounds induce cell cycle arrest. Among the tested compounds, MON displayed the strongest anti-proliferative effect on A549 cells, while MON, **3a**, and **3f** exhibited comparable efficacy in inducing cell arrest in MDA-MB-231 cells.

2.2.3. Induction of apoptosis

The pro-apoptotic activities of MON and its derivatives (**3a**, **3f**, and **6**) were assessed via flow cytometry using an Annexin V-FITC/PI

Table 1
Antiproliferative activity (IC₅₀, μM) of monensin (MON) and its derivatives estimated by the MTT assay [32].

Compound	Cancer cells					Normal cells	
	SW480	SW620	PC3	MDA-MB-231	A549	HaCaT	V79
	IC ₅₀						
(MON)	0.69 ± 0.15	0.92 ± 0.08	0.62 ± 0.04	2.11 ± 0.02	0.74 ± 0.03	0.62 ± 0.04	0.91 ± 0.07
3a	0.71 ± 0.02	1.05 ± 0.10	0.52 ± 0.12	0.97 ± 0.20	0.82 ± 0.09	1.21 ± 0.42	1.31 ± 0.15
3b	0.57 ± 0.06	0.89 ± 0.19	0.59 ± 0.19	0.72 ± 0.08	0.92 ± 0.13	0.84 ± 0.11	0.72 ± 0.02
3c	0.57 ± 0.01	0.96 ± 0.21	0.50 ± 0.11	0.93 ± 0.29	0.84 ± 0.01	0.91 ± 0.14	0.76 ± 0.01
3d	0.74 ± 0.03	0.65 ± 0.04	0.48 ± 0.09	0.66 ± 0.17	0.68 ± 0.01	0.74 ± 0.13	0.76 ± 0.11
3e	0.57 ± 0.02	0.86 ± 0.21	0.97 ± 0.22	0.69 ± 0.10	0.89 ± 0.20	0.89 ± 0.21	0.65 ± 0.08
3f	4.32 ± 1.40	1.35 ± 0.08	1.11 ± 0.06	2.66 ± 0.14	0.80 ± 0.10	1.72 ± 0.21	0.61 ± 0.07
5a	0.91 ± 0.37	0.75 ± 0.07	0.61 ± 0.07	0.84 ± 0.35	1.19 ± 0.22	0.80 ± 0.09	0.70 ± 0.04
5b	2.60 ± 1.15	0.90 ± 0.11	1.16 ± 0.15	1.38 ± 0.03	1.07 ± 0.01	1.19 ± 0.09	0.75 ± 0.02
5c	0.71 ± 0.07	0.74 ± 0.13	0.77 ± 0.13	0.88 ± 0.17	0.95 ± 0.05	0.88 ± 0.15	0.62 ± 0.07
5d	2.00 ± 0.03	0.88 ± 0.15	0.82 ± 0.05	0.91 ± 0.28	0.75 ± 0.01	0.88 ± 0.19	0.48 ± 0.04
5e	2.68 ± 1.16	1.12 ± 0.08	0.79 ± 0.08	1.24 ± 0.11	0.81 ± 0.03	1.24 ± 0.33	0.68 ± 0.14
5f	0.91 ± 0.33	0.94 ± 0.04	0.81 ± 0.17	1.71 ± 0.31	1.01 ± 0.01	1.31 ± 0.31	0.55 ± 0.02
6	2.87 ± 0.75	10.98 ± 1.0	5.22 ± 0.79	33.96 ± 1.6	4.97 ± 1.67	8.51 ± 0.79	1.71 ± 0.24
DOX	0.29 ± 0.08	0.31 ± 0.08	0.59 ± 0.02	0.83 ± 0.03	0.63 ± 0.2	0.29 ± 0.01	2.01 ± 0.03

Data are expressed as the mean ± SD. IC₅₀ (μM) is the concentration of the compound that corresponds to a 50 % growth inhibition of cell line (as compared to the control) after culturing the cells for 72 h with the studied compound. Human primary colon cancer cells (SW480); human metastatic colon cancer cells (SW620); human metastatic prostate cancer cells (PC3); human breast cancer cells (MDA-MB-231); human lung cancer cells (A549); human immortal keratinocyte cells (HaCaT); Chinese hamster lung fibroblasts (V79). Doxorubicin (DOX) – the selected reference compound commonly used in cancer treatment.

Table 2
The calculated values of the selectivity indices (SI) for HaCaT (left side) and V79 (right side) non-tumor cell lines.

Compound	HaCaT					V79				
	SW480	SW620	PC3	MDA-MB-231	A549	SW480	SW620	PC3	MDA-MB-231	A549
1 (MON)	0.9	0.7	1.0	0.3	0.8	1.3	1.0	1.5	0.4	1.2
3a	1.7	1.2	2.3	1.2	1.5	1.8	1.2	2.5	1.4	1.6
3b	1.5	0.9	1.4	1.1	0.9	1.3	0.8	1.4	1.0	0.8
3c	1.6	0.9	1.8	1.0	1.1	1.3	0.8	1.5	0.8	0.9
3d	1.0	1.1	1.8	1.1	1.1	1.0	1.2	1.6	1.2	1.1
3e	1.6	1.0	0.9	1.3	1.0	1.1	0.8	0.7	0.9	0.7
3f	0.4	1.3	1.5	0.6	2.2	0.1	0.5	0.5	0.2	0.8
5a	0.9	1.1	1.3	0.9	0.7	0.8	0.9	1.1	0.8	0.6
5b	0.5	1.3	1.0	0.9	1.1	0.3	0.8	0.6	0.5	0.7
5c	1.2	1.2	1.1	1.0	0.9	0.9	0.8	0.8	0.7	0.7
5d	0.4	1.0	1.1	1.0	1.2	0.2	0.5	0.6	0.5	0.6
5e	0.5	1.1	1.6	1.0	1.5	0.3	0.6	0.9	0.5	0.8
5f	1.4	1.4	1.6	0.8	1.3	0.6	0.6	0.7	0.3	0.5
6	3.0	0.8	1.6	0.3	1.7	0.6	0.2	0.3	0.1	0.3
DOX	1.0	0.9	0.5	0.3	0.5	6.9	6.5	3.4	2.4	3.2

SI = IC₅₀ for normal cell line/IC₅₀ for cancer cell line.

binding assay under 72 h treatment conditions in A549 and MDA-MB-231 cell lines. This study quantitatively evaluated early apoptosis, late apoptosis, and necrosis to provide a comprehensive profile of the cytotoxic effects exerted by these compounds.

In both A549 and MDA-MB-231 cell lines, the treatment with MON demonstrated potent pro-apoptotic effects. MON induced a substantial increase in late apoptotic cells, with 52.53 % in A549 and 45.38 % in MDA-MB-231, alongside a marked elevation in early apoptosis (20.26 % and 22.54 %, respectively) (Figs. 4 and 5). These findings underscore MON's robust cytotoxic efficacy across both cell lines.

For derivative 3a, late apoptosis was notably elevated relative to controls, accounting for 25 % in MDA-MB-231 and 12.77 % in A549 cells. Compound 3f induced apoptosis primarily in MDA-MB-231 cells, with significant contributions from both early (16.43 %) and late (27.76 %) apoptosis (Figs. 4 and 5). Interestingly, while derivatives 3f and 6 showed only a modest induction of apoptosis in A549 cells, compound 6 in MDA-MB-231 cells emerged as a significant inducer of late apoptosis (12.95 %), suggesting that its cytotoxic effects may be more specific to this cell line (Figs. 4 and 5).

To sum up, MON demonstrated pronounced cytotoxicity characterized by the strong induction of both early and late apoptosis in A549 and MDA-MB-231 cells. Compound 3a showed pro-apoptotic activity in both cancer cell lines while derivative 3f exhibited cell line-specific effects, with enhanced efficacy in MDA-MB-231 cells. These observations highlight the potential of 3a and 3f as therapeutic agents with robust apoptotic induction, albeit with variable efficacies across different cancer cell types. Further studies are needed to elucidate the molecular mechanisms underlying their selective cytotoxicity and optimize their potential for clinical applications.

2.2.4. Mitochondrial membrane potential

Mitochondrial membrane potential (ΔΨ_m) determined by the fluorescence-based method in the JC-10 assay is a critical parameter reflecting mitochondrial function and health in cells. This assay is widely employed in studies on apoptosis, and mitochondrial dysfunction as well as in drug screening, as the loss of mitochondrial membrane potential is an early indicator of apoptosis. The present study revealed a decrease in ΔΨ_m after 48 h of treatment with MON and its derivatives,

Fig. 3. The effect of MON and its derivatives on the cell cycle of A549 and MDA-MB-231 cells. The bars represent the effect of MON, 3a, 3f and 6 on the percent of cells in particular cell cycle phases. The cells were incubated for 24 h with the compounds at their IC₅₀ concentrations, stained with PI and analyzed by flow cytometry. Untreated cells were used as the control. The results are presented by means ± SD, n = 4. Statistical significance was determined at p < 0.05 (*); p < 0.01 (**); p < 0.001 (***) and p < 0.0001 (****) by 1-way ANOVA.

Fig. 4. The effect of MON and its derivatives on the apoptosis of A549 and MDA-MB-231 cells. The bars represent % of live cells, the cells at the early and late stage of apoptosis and necrosis. The cells were incubated for 72 h with the compounds at their IC₅₀ concentrations, stained with Annexin V-FITC and PI and analyzed by flow cytometry. Untreated cells were used as the control. The results are presented by means ± SD, n = 4. Statistical significance was determined at p < 0.05 (*); p < 0.01 (**); p < 0.001 (***) and p < 0.0001 (****) by 1-way ANOVA.

Fig. 5. Representative results (%) as dot plots showing apoptosis of A549 and MDA-MB-231 cells after treatment with MON and its derivatives 3a, 3f, 6, analyzed by flow cytometry.

which is a hallmark of mitochondrial dysfunction and early apoptosis.

Elevated green fluorescence, informing about the content of JC-10 monomers, was observed mainly with MDA-MB-231 cells, indicating a pronounced sensitivity of these cells to the treatment with MON and its derivatives (Figs. 6 and 7). The highest percentage of green fluorescent monomers was observed for compound 3f at 87.9 %, followed by 3a at

78.26 % and MON at 76.65 % (Figs. 6 and 7). The sensitivity of A549 cells to treatment with MON was similar (84 %), with a lower decrease in $\Delta\Psi_m$ after treatment with 3a and 3f (21.33 % and 11.34 % of green monomers, respectively) (Figs. 6 and 7). Notably, compound 6 exhibited a higher effect on MDA-MB-231 (26.67 %) than A549 cells (4.74 %) (Figs. 6 and 7). This finding aligns with the results of the Annexin V-

Fig. 6. Flow cytometry analysis of changes in the mitochondrial membrane potential in A549 and MDA-MB-231 cells after treatment with MON, its derivatives 3a, 3f, 6 and carbonylcyanide-*m*-chlorophenylhydrazine (CCCP) for 48 h, at their IC_{50} concentrations. Untreated cells were used as the control. The bars represent the proportion of cells (%) showing green or red fluorescence. The results are presented by means \pm SD, $n = 4$. Statistical significance was determined at $p < 0.05$ (*); $p < 0.01$ (**); $p < 0.001$ (***) and $p < 0.0001$ (****) by 1-way ANOVA.

Fig. 7. Results of a representative experiment of JC-10 fluorescence assays in A549 and MDA-MB-231 cells, after treatment with MON and its derivatives 3a, 3f, 6, analyzed by flow cytometry.

FITC/PI binding assay, further supporting the heightened susceptibility of MDA-MB-231 cells to mitochondrial depolarization and apoptotic induction by **MON** and its derivatives.

To recapitulate, different cancer cells display changes in $\Delta\Psi_m$ depending on their metabolic properties. Variations in mitochondrial dynamics, such as mitochondrial fusion and fission, also have impact on $\Delta\Psi_m$ and uptake of JC-10 dye across different types of cancer cells.

2.2.5. Mitochondria activity

MitoTracker Red and Green staining were used in flow cytometry to evaluate mitochondrial function ($\Delta\Psi_m$) and mass. The obtained results revealed that MTGreen staining of A549 cells treated with **MON** and MDA-MB-231 cells treated with **3a** and **3f** demonstrated the highest, 8-fold increase in mean fluorescence intensity (MFI) in comparison to controls, and the percentages of MT Green stained positive cells were 83.6 %, 95 % and 88.6 %, respectively (Figs. 8 and 9). Additionally, above 70 % of MTGreen positive cells were observed in response to **MON** in MDA-MB-231 cells and to **3a** in A549 cells (Figs. 8 and 9). Moreover, MDA-MB-231 cells were also sensitive to the treatment with compound **6** showing 51 % of MT Green positive cells, while for A549 cell line a moderately elevated level of MT Green positive cells was found (Figs. 8 and 9). Consistent with the apoptosis and JC-10 assay results, the MitoTracker Green data showed that MDA-MB-231 cells exhibited a more dynamic response, which could indicate a higher sensitivity to treatment with **MON** and its derivatives (**3a**, **3f**, and **6**) compared to A549 cells.

In contrast to the MT Green dye, only a slight, insignificant increase in MitoTracker CMXRos staining was observed in response to all tested compounds in both cancer cell lines. It was found, that both mean fluorescence intensity (MFI) and the percentage of CMXRos-positive cells were similar to the levels in the controls (Figs. 8 and 9).

In conclusion, the high MFI and increased percentage of MitoTracker Green-positive cells, combined with MitoTracker Red levels comparable to those of the controls, might suggest that mitochondrial mass increased, without a significant improvement in mitochondrial membrane potential ($\Delta\Psi_m$). The observed increase in MitoTracker Green fluorescence, possibly a result of mitochondrial fission, indicated an increase in mitochondrial mass or density, which is often associated with specific cellular processes. These findings may reflect a defensive mechanism of cancer cells against the action of **MON** and its derivatives. However, MitoTracker Red levels comparable to those in the controls

suggest that the membrane potential ($\Delta\Psi_m$) remains unchanged, implying that the newly formed mitochondria are not functioning at the same energy state as the control cells.

2.2.6. ROS production

In this study the CellROX Green Reagent was used to quantitatively assess reactive oxygen species (ROS) in live cells. Upon oxidation, this reagent becomes DNA-bound, resulting in its fluorescence signal being predominantly localized in the nucleus and mitochondria, which are key sites of oxidative stress.

The experimental results revealed that ROS levels were the highest after treatment with **MON** alone, in both cancer cell lines (Fig. 10). In turn, the treatment with compounds **3a** and **3f** led to an elevated ROS generation with a 2-fold increase for A549 and a 1.5-fold increase for MDA-MB-231 cells, in comparison to the levels in the control cells (Fig. 10). Conversely, treatment with compound **6** resulted in only a marginal and statistically insignificant elevation in ROS levels in both cell lines (Fig. 10).

These findings suggest differential cellular responses to **MON** derivatives. A549 cells exhibited pronounced ROS generation in response to **MON** and its derivatives, potentially indicating higher oxidative stress sensitivity. However, subsequent analyses, including assessments of mitochondrial membrane potential (MMP) and apoptosis, suggest that despite their heightened ROS production, A549 cells demonstrate greater resistance to **MON** and its derivatives than MDA-MB-231 cells. This apparent paradox underscores the complexity of cancer cell responses to oxidative stress.

2.2.7. Antimicrobial activity

Because **MON**, like the other ionophores, exhibits high antibacterial activity, all the compounds obtained were tested for their antimicrobial properties against eight bacterial strains: five standard Gram-positive bacteria (*S. aureus* NCTC 4163, ATCC 25923, ATCC 6538, and ATCC 29213; *S. epidermidis* ATCC 12228 and ATCC 35984) and two Gram-negative strains (*E. coli* ATCC 25922 and *P. aeruginosa* ATCC 15442). Similar to **MON**, all analogs (**3a–5f**) exhibited high antimicrobial activity against Gram-positive bacteria and no activity against Gram-negative bacterial strain (Table 3). However, compounds **3b** and **5b** (tri(*p*-tolyl)phosphine derivatives) were more active against the Gram-negative bacterial strain *P. aeruginosa* than all other analogs and **MON** itself (Table 3). Moreover, all the obtained salts were more active than

Fig. 8. Flow cytometry analysis of MitoTracker Red CMXRos and MitoTracker Green FM mitochondrial staining in A549 and MDA-MB-231 cells after treatment with **MON** and its derivatives **3a**, **3f**, and **6** for 48 h at their IC_{50} concentrations. Untreated cells were used as the control. The bars represent the fold change in mean fluorescent intensity (left panel) and % of MitoTrackers positive cells as compared to the control (right panel). The results are presented by means \pm SD, $n = 4$. Statistical significance was determined at $p < 0.05$ (*); $p < 0.01$ (**); $p < 0.001$ (***) and $p < 0.0001$ (****) by 1-way ANOVA.

Fig. 9. Results of a representative experiment by MitoTracker Red CMXRos and MitoTracker Green FM fluorescence assays of A549 and MDA-MB-231 cells after treatment with MON and its derivatives 3a, 3f, 6, analyzed by flow cytometry.

Fig. 10. The effect of MON and its derivatives **3a**, **3f**, and **6** on ROS production in A549 and MDA-MB-231 cells. The bars show the fold change in mean fluorescent intensity as compared to the control. The cells were incubated for 6 h with the compounds at their IC_{50} concentrations, labeled with CellROX Geen Reagent and analyzed by microplate-based fluorimetry. Untreated cells were used as the control. The results are presented by means \pm SD, $n = 4$. Statistical significance was determined at $p < 0.05$ (*); $p < 0.01$ (**); $p < 0.001$ (***) and $p < 0.0001$ (****), by 2-way ANOVA.

Table 3

The MIC values (in $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$) of monensin, its benzyl ester, and all conjugates against Gram-positive and Gram-negative bacteria strains.

Compound	Reference strains of Gram(+) and Gram(-) bacteria							
	<i>S. aureus</i> NCTC 4163	<i>S. aureus</i> ATCC 25923	<i>S. aureus</i> ATCC 6538	<i>S. aureus</i> ATCC 29213	<i>S. epidermidis</i> ATCC 12228	<i>S. epidermidis</i> ATCC 35984	<i>E. coli</i> ATCC 25922	<i>P. aeruginosa</i> ATCC 15442
	MIC	MIC	MIC	MIC	MIC	MIC	MIC	MIC
1 (MON)	2	1	2	1	2	2	na	na
3a	2	2	2	2	2	2	>256	>256
3b	1	2	2	2	2	2	256	128
3c	2	2	2	2	2	2	>256	>256
3d	2	2	2	2	2	2	>256	>256
3e	2	2	2	2	2	2	256	>256
3f	4	4	4	4	4	4	>256	>256
5a	1	1	1	1	1	1	256	256
5b	2	2	2	2	2	2	>256	128
5c	2	2	2	2	2	2	>256	>256
5d	2	2	2	2	2	2	>256	>256
5e	2	2	2	4	2	2	256	256
5f	4	4	4	4	4	4	>256	>256
6	>256	>256	>256	>256	>256	>256	>256	>256
CIP	0.125	0.25	0.125	0.25	0.125	0.125	0.0075	0.125

na = no activity.

MON benzyl ester **6**. The conjugates with triphenylphosphine or its analogs (**3a–3e** and **5a–5e**) were more active than their aliphatic counterparts **3f** and **5f**, suggesting the necessity of an aromatic moiety for the antimicrobial activity of such hybrids (Table 3). Some of the analogs showed even higher activity than MON, particularly compound **5a**, which showed an MIC value of $1 \mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ for all the tested strains of Gram-positive bacteria (Table 3). However, none of the compounds showed higher activity than ciprofloxacin, which is commonly used in treatment (Table 3).

2.3. Biophysical studies

2.3.1. Mitochondrial respiration rate

Changes in cellular respiration in the presence of MON and its derivatives were examined using an Oxygraph-2K system. To determine the respiration rate of A549 cells, the high-resolution respirometry was applied to measure oxygen consumption. The measurements were conducted in live non-permeabilized cells to analyze the effect of MON and its analogs on mitochondria and their ability to aggregate in these organelles reflected by changes in the respiration rate of A549 cells. FCCP was administered to achieve the maximal respiration rate. As shown in

Fig. 11. The effect of **MON** and its derivatives on the oxygen consumption rate in the non-perforated A549 cell model in starving DMEM (Dulbecco Minimal Essential Medium). The bars represent the effect of the tested compounds at different concentrations: 0.1, 0.3, 1, 3, and 10 μM on A549 cell oxygen consumption rate, measured by the high-resolution respirometry. The effect of the tested compounds: a) monensin A (**MON**), b) **3a**, c) **3b**, d) **3e**, e) **6**, f) **3f** was compared to the oxygen consumption rate measured after stabilization before addition of any compounds. Complete uncoupling was induced by 1 μM FCCP. The results are represented by means \pm SD, $n = 4$. Statistical significance was determined at $p < 0.01$ (**) and $p < 0.001$ (***) by 1-way ANOVA.

Fig. 11a, **MON** did not change the oxygen respiration rate at any of the applied concentration. FCCP was used to show the proper functioning of cells by the full uncoupling of mitochondria. A slight decrease in the oxygen consumption rate was observed upon exposure to compound **6** (**Fig. 11e**), while FCCP did not perform full uncoupling of mitochondria. Compound **3e** (**Fig. 11d**) caused an increase in oxygen consumption at concentrations of up to 10 μM , which resulted in mitochondria disability by a decreased respiration rate in concentrations of 3 and 10 μM . A similar decrease in oxygen consumption rate was observed in the presence of compound **3b** (**Fig. 11c**), which was the most active among the compounds examined at a concentration of 1 μM . Conjugates **3a** (**Figs. 11b**) and **3f** (**Fig. 11f**) were effective at concentrations of 3 and 10 μM , respectively, with fully uncoupled mitochondria before the addition of FCCP.

2.3.2. Interaction of monensin A and its derivatives with lipid membranes

To prove the electrophysiological activity of the tested compounds, we performed black lipid membrane experiments in gradient solutions 50/150 mM NaCl (*cis/trans*). The applied experimental voltages varied from -60 mV to $+60$ mV. After assessment of the activity of the tested compounds by oxygraph examination, we chose three compounds **3a** (**Fig. 12b**), **3e** (**Figs. 12c**), and **6** (**Fig. 12d**), to check their ion transport capability. Unmodified **MON** (**Fig. 12a**) did not change the ionic current

flow through the azolectin bilayer membrane at concentration up to 10 μM . A similar effect was observed for the uncharged benzyl ester of **MON** (compound **6**, **Fig. 12d**). Also, no significant decrease in ion current flow was noted for the concentration of 10 μM as expected on the basis of oxygraph experiments. The other compounds studied were capable of current generation in a dose-dependent manner. Similar to the results of the oxygraph experiments, the increase in ionic current flow was pronounced for conjugates **3a** and **3b** at concentrations above 3 μM and 1 μM , respectively. Based on the high values of ionic current, conjugate **3e** showed far more electrophysiological activity than **3a**. Examples of recorded signals are presented in **Fig. 11a**, **11b**, **11c**, and **11d**. The two compounds alternated the basal ionic current but did not perform any open or close states as observed in typical channels. The current flow was smooth without any jagged traces.

3. Conclusions

The syntheses of a series of novel phosphonium salts of monensin A (**MON**) are described. These compounds can be obtained by simple nucleophilic substitution or esterification reactions, which provide convenient access to an extensive library of derivatives that are interesting for medicinal chemistry and cell biology. The desired compounds were obtained with the yields of 14–43%. Furthermore, for comparative

Fig. 12. Current-time recordings of ionic current flow through the lipid bilayer membranes and current-voltage (*i-v*) relationship measured in a gradient of 50/150 mM NaCl (*cis/trans*). The left panel shows representative recordings in the control and in the presence of 3 or 10 μM (a) monensin A (MON), and (b, c, d) its derivatives at a potential of -60 mV. The right panel represents current-voltage characteristics in the presence of (a) monensin A (MON), (b) 3a, (c) 3e, and (d) 6 at concentrations of 0.1, 0.3, 1, 3, and 10 μM at potentials of -60 , -40 , -20 , 0, 20, 40, and 60 mV. The average current values at the voltages and their standard deviations (SD) are marked on the chart. The experiment was performed in four repetitions. The symbol “—” indicates the control level of the current in the absence of the compounds studied, the symbol “ \uparrow ” indicates the representative amplitude of the measured current in the presence of each conjugate studied. Statistical significance was determined at $p < 0.001$ (***) by 1-way ANOVA.

purposes, the synthesis of MON benzyl ester (compound 6) was also performed, with a yield of 77 %. With respect to the antiproliferative activity, it should be noted that many of the obtained compounds exhibit lower IC_{50} values and higher selectivity indices than MON. Good examples are compounds 3a and 3f, which not only inhibited the growth of prostate cancer cells (PC3) and human lung cancer cells (A549) but were also characterized by higher SI values, highlighting their prospective

therapeutic use. Moreover, compounds 3a, 3c, and 3d exhibited more potent anticancer effects towards the PC3 cell line than doxorubicin – a commonly used anticancer drug. Additionally, the benzyl ester of MON (compound 6) exhibited the lowest activity among the tested analogs, proving the necessity of TPP^+ moiety in the structure of the MON derivatives to obtain the desired effects. The steric factor is also important in the design of new derivatives, as 4-carbon linked conjugates showed

higher activity and selectivity than their 6-carbon linked counterparts. Since, the main objective of the conducted research was to determine whether the obtained conjugates were targeted to the mitochondria of cancer cells, studies on mitochondrial membrane potential and activity were carried out. **MON** caused mitochondrial potential dissipation in both the A549 and MDA-MB-231 cell lines. However, derivatives **3a** and **3f** induced green fluorescence of JC-10 mainly in the MDA-MB-231 line, indicating its high sensitivity to **MON** derivatives. These data are in good correlation with the Annexin V-FITC/PI binding assay, confirming that the studied conjugates induce apoptosis in cancer cells, among other mechanisms, by dissipating their mitochondrial potential. Furthermore, MitoTracker Green data confirmed the increased sensitivity of the MDA-MB-231 cell line to the tested compounds compared to that of the A549 cell line. MDA-MB-231 cells treated with **3a** and **3f** demonstrated an 8-fold increase in mean fluorescence intensity compared to that of the controls. The mitochondrial activity of the tested compounds was also confirmed in biophysical studies. The study conducted using the Oxygraph-2K system showed that unmodified **MON** did not change the oxygen respiration rate of A549 cells. Its derivatives, on the other hand, demonstrated very potent activity; compounds **3a** and **3f** induced changes in the oxygen respiration rate at concentrations of 3 and 10 μM , respectively, while the highest effectiveness was observed for compound **3b**, which led to a decrease in the oxygen consumption rate after reaching the max level at a concentration of 1 μM . The results of the study on the Oxygraph-2K system were also confirmed by the black lipid membrane experiment. **MON** and its benzyl ester **6** did not change the ionic current flow through the azolectin bilayer membrane at concentration of up to 10 μM . On the other hand, conjugates **3a** and **3e** were capable of current generation in a dose-dependent manner, confirming their capability for ionic transport. In summary, it has been demonstrated that the conjugates are efficiently transported into the mitochondria of cancer cells, where they induce mitochondrial uncoupling and an increased rate of respiration, ultimately leading to apoptosis. The strategy of bioconjugation may contribute to development of novel, effective drug candidates that, owing to their high efficacy and selectivity, hold potential for application in chemotherapy.

4. Experimental

4.1. General procedures

Monensin A (**MON**) was isolated in the form of sodium salt (**MON-Na**) from premix Coxidin® (commercially available veterinary feed additive). **MON** was obtained from **MON-Na** by the extraction with H_2SO_4 (pH = 1.5) in CH_2Cl_2 as previously described [33,34]. All other reagents were commercially available and purchased from Merck or Trimen Chemicals S.A., and were used without further purification. Compounds **2**, **4**, and **6** were synthesized according to the protocol published previously [18]. A comprehensive description of the general procedures, equipment, and measurement parameters can be found in the Supplementary material.

4.2. Synthesis of 4-bromobutyric ester of monensin A (compound 2)

MON (1.0 g, 1.49 mmol, 1.0 equiv.) was dissolved in toluene (30 mL) and the solution was then heated to 90 °C. After 15 min, DBU (386 mg, 2.53 mmol, 1.7 equiv.) was added dropwise to the reaction mixture, and after another 20 min 1,4-dibromobutane (965 mg, 4.47 mmol, 3.0 equiv.) was added dropwise. After a few minutes, the color of the solution changed to brown. The resulting solution was stirred for the next 24 h. The reaction mixture was then concentrated on a rotary evaporator. Purification on silica gel using the CombiFlash system (0%→50% EtOAc/hexane) gave the pure ester **2** as a colorless oil. After twice co-evaporation to dryness with *n*-pentane, the product remained in an oily form (700 mg, 58% yield). The spectroscopic data were in agreement with previously published data [18].

4.3. General procedure for preparation of phosphonium salts of monensin A with butane-like linker (analogs 3a–3f)

Compound **2** (400 mg, 0.50 mmol, 1.0 equiv.) was dissolved in CH_3CN (30 mL) and the respective phosphine (1.50 mmol, 3.0 equiv.) was added upon stirring. The solution was heated under reflux for 72 h. Subsequently, the reaction mixture was concentrated on a rotary evaporator. Purification on silica gel using the CombiFlash system (0%→40% acetone/ CHCl_3) gave the phosphonium salts of **MON** as colorless oils. After twice co-evaporation to dryness with *n*-pentane, the oily products were completely converted into white amorphous solids.

Phosphonium salt 3a: 74 mg, 14% yield. Isolated as a white amorphous solid, a single spot by TLC. UV-active and stains green with PMA; ^1H NMR (400 MHz, CD_3CN) δ 7.92–7.68 (m, 15H), 5.78 (d, J = 1.3 Hz, 1H), 5.53–5.50 (m, 1H), 4.37 (ddd, J = 9.5, 7.2, 4.1 Hz, 1H), 4.20–4.03 (m, 4H), 4.03–3.92 (m, 2H), 3.84–3.79 (m, 1H), 3.69 (dd, J = 5.3, 2.9 Hz, 1H), 3.67–3.53 (m, 3H), 3.49–3.41 (m, 1H), 3.38 (ddd, J = 10.1, 4.0, 1.7 Hz, 1H), 2.83 (ddd, J = 13.8, 6.8, 2.8 Hz, 1H), 2.60 (s, 1H), 2.34 (s, 1H), 2.31–2.22 (m, 2H), 2.17–0.63 (m, 48H) ppm; ^{13}C NMR (101 MHz, CD_3CN) δ 176.0, 135.8, 135.8, 134.6, 134.5, 131.1, 131.0, 119.6, 118.7, 108.4, 99.0, 86.6, 86.4, 84.6, 81.8, 81.6, 76.3, 74.7, 69.6, 69.1, 67.0, 63.8, 58.4, 55.2, 41.3, 39.9, 36.8, 36.5, 36.3, 35.5, 35.1, 34.6, 33.4, 33.2, 32.2, 30.4, 30.1, 30.0, 29.7, 29.6, 28.3, 26.8, 22.6, 22.1, 20.0, 20.0, 16.4, 16.1, 14.5, 13.2, 11.5, 10.8, 8.1 ppm; ^{31}P NMR (122 MHz, CN_3CN) δ 25.2 ppm; HRMS (ESI⁺) m/z : [M]⁺ Calcd for $\text{C}_{58}\text{H}_{84}\text{O}_{11}\text{P}^+$ 987.5746; Found 987.5745.

Phosphonium salt 3b: 99 mg, 18% yield. Isolated as a white amorphous solid, a single spot by TLC. UV-active and stains green with PMA; ^1H NMR (401 MHz, CD_3CN) δ 7.67–7.48 (m, 12H), 5.79–5.75 (m, 1H), 5.51 (dd, J = 3.0, 1.6 Hz, 1H), 4.36 (ddd, J = 9.4, 7.2, 4.1 Hz, 1H), 4.17–4.09 (m, 1H), 4.09–4.00 (m, 2H), 4.00–3.90 (m, 3H), 3.80–3.76 (m, 1H), 3.67 (dd, J = 5.2, 2.8 Hz, 1H), 3.66–3.56 (m, 2H), 3.52–3.44 (m, 1H), 3.36 (ddd, J = 9.7, 3.8, 1.5 Hz, 1H), 3.30–3.19 (m, 1H), 2.86–2.78 (m, 1H), 2.58 (s, 1H), 2.27 (s, 9H), 2.17–0.65 (m, 51H) ppm; ^{13}C NMR (101 MHz, CD_3CN) δ 176.3, 147.4, 147.4, 134.7, 134.6, 132.0, 131.9, 116.8, 115.9, 108.7, 99.3, 86.9, 86.7, 84.9, 82.1, 81.8, 76.6, 75.1, 69.9, 69.5, 67.3, 64.1, 58.5, 55.4, 41.6, 40.2, 37.0, 36.6, 36.5, 35.8, 35.4, 34.9, 33.6, 33.5, 32.5, 30.6, 30.4, 30.3, 29.9, 29.8, 28.5, 27.1, 23.1, 22.6, 21.9, 21.9, 20.3, 20.2, 16.6, 16.3, 14.7, 13.5, 11.7, 10.9, 8.3 ppm; ^{31}P NMR (122 MHz, CD_3CN) δ 24.1 ppm; HRMS (ESI⁺) m/z : [M]⁺ Calcd for $\text{C}_{61}\text{H}_{90}\text{O}_{11}\text{P}^+$ 1029.6215; Found 1029.6215.

Phosphonium salt 3c: 207 mg, 36% yield. Isolated as a white amorphous solid, a single spot by TLC. UV-active and stains green with PMA; ^1H NMR (400 MHz, CD_3CN) δ 7.70–7.61 (m, 6H), 7.23–7.16 (m, 6H), 5.77 (d, J = 1.4 Hz, 1H), 5.49 (dd, J = 3.3, 1.8 Hz, 1H), 4.36 (ddd, J = 9.6, 7.2, 4.0 Hz, 1H), 4.17–4.01 (m, 3H), 4.00–3.92 (m, 2H), 3.89 (s, 9H), 3.80–3.75 (m, 1H), 3.70–3.66 (m, 1H), 3.65–3.55 (m, 2H), 3.44–3.33 (m, 2H), 2.82 (ddd, J = 13.8, 6.9, 2.6 Hz, 1H), 2.40–0.62 (m, 54H) ppm; ^{13}C NMR (101 MHz, CD_3CN) δ 176.1, 165.4, 165.4, 136.5, 136.4, 116.8, 116.6, 110.7, 109.8, 108.5, 99.1, 86.7, 86.4, 84.7, 81.9, 81.6, 76.4, 74.8, 69.7, 69.3, 67.1, 64.0, 58.4, 56.6, 55.2, 41.3, 40.0, 36.8, 36.4, 36.3, 35.6, 35.1, 34.7, 33.4, 33.3, 32.3, 32.1, 30.4, 30.2, 30.0, 29.7, 29.6, 28.3, 26.9, 23.5, 23.0, 20.0, 20.0, 16.5, 16.1, 14.6, 13.3, 11.5, 10.8, 8.1 ppm; ^{31}P NMR (122 MHz, CD_3CN) δ 22.8 ppm; HRMS (ESI⁺) m/z : [M]⁺ Calcd for $\text{C}_{61}\text{H}_{90}\text{O}_{14}\text{P}^+$ 1077.6063; Found 1077.6084.

Phosphonium salt 3d: 190 mg, 33% yield. Isolated as a white amorphous solid, a single spot by TLC. UV-active and stains green with PMA; ^1H NMR (400 MHz, CD_3CN) δ 7.82–7.74 (m, 3H), 7.32–7.21 (m, 6H), 7.21–7.13 (m, 3H), 5.85 (d, J = 1.1 Hz, 1H), 5.58 (dd, J = 3.0, 1.7 Hz, 1H), 4.35 (ddd, J = 9.5, 7.2, 4.0 Hz, 1H), 4.11 (dt, J = 11.0, 6.1 Hz, 1H), 4.04 (d, J = 3.4 Hz, 1H), 4.02 (s, 1H), 4.00–3.91 (m, 3H), 3.86–3.80 (m, 1H), 3.72 (s, 9H), 3.67–3.62 (m, 2H), 3.62–3.56 (m, J = 10.0, 5.8 Hz, 2H), 3.37 (d, J = 9.8 Hz, 1H), 3.30–3.11 (m, 3H), 2.81 (ddd, J = 13.8, 6.9, 2.7 Hz, 1H), 2.43–0.63 (m, 50H) ppm; ^{13}C NMR (101 MHz, CD_3CN) δ 176.0, 162.5, 162.5, 137.6, 137.6, 135.8, 135.7, 122.9, 122.7, 113.7,

113.6, 108.5, 107.4, 106.5, 99.1, 86.7, 86.4, 84.6, 81.8, 81.6, 76.3, 74.8, 69.9, 69.7, 69.3, 67.1, 64.5, 58.3, 56.9, 55.2, 41.5, 40.0, 36.7, 36.5, 36.3, 35.5, 35.2, 34.7, 33.5, 33.3, 32.3, 32.1, 30.4, 30.4, 30.2, 29.7, 29.6, 28.3, 26.9, 24.4, 23.9, 21.6, 21.5, 16.4, 16.1, 14.6, 13.2, 11.5, 10.9, 8.1 ppm; ^{31}P NMR (122 MHz, CD_3CN) δ 26.3 ppm; HRMS (ESI^+) m/z : $[\text{M}]^+$ Calcd for $\text{C}_{61}\text{H}_{90}\text{O}_{14}\text{P}^+$ 1077.6063; Found 1077.6076.

Phosphonium salt 3e: 187 mg, 34 % yield. Isolated as a white amorphous solid, a single spot by TLC. UV-active and stains green with PMA; ^1H NMR (400 MHz, CD_3CN) δ 7.88–7.62 (m, 9H), 7.57–7.39 (m, 3H), 6.95–6.82 (m, 2H), 5.78 (d, $J = 1.5$ Hz, 1H), 5.53 (dd, $J = 3.2, 1.7$ Hz, 1H), 4.34 (ddd, $J = 9.6, 7.2, 4.1$ Hz, 1H), 4.20 (dd, $J = 3.7, 3.0$ Hz, 1H), 4.16–4.00 (m, 3H), 4.00–3.90 (m, 2H), 3.83–3.77 (m, 1H), 3.68 (dd, $J = 5.4, 2.6$ Hz, 1H), 3.66–3.54 (m, 2H), 3.52–3.20 (m, 4H), 3.04 (s, 6H), 2.81 (ddd, $J = 13.7, 6.8, 2.6$ Hz, 1H), 2.39 (s, 1H), 2.31–2.20 (m, 2H), 2.17–0.60 (m, 48H) ppm; ^{13}C NMR (101 MHz, CD_3CN) δ 176.0, 154.9, 135.7, 135.6, 135.3, 135.3, 134.3, 134.2, 130.9, 130.8, 121.4, 120.6, 113.3, 113.2, 108.4, 99.0, 86.7, 86.4, 84.6, 81.8, 81.5, 76.3, 74.7, 69.6, 69.3, 67.0, 63.9, 58.4, 41.2, 40.1, 39.9, 36.8, 36.4, 36.3, 35.5, 35.1, 34.6, 33.4, 33.2, 32.2, 30.4, 30.2, 30.0, 29.7, 29.6, 28.4, 26.9, 23.1, 22.6, 20.04, 20.00, 16.4, 16.1, 14.5, 13.2, 11.4, 10.8, 8.2 ppm; ^{31}P NMR (122 MHz, CD_3CN) δ 23.5 ppm; HRMS (ESI^+) m/z : $[\text{M}]^+$ Calcd for $\text{C}_{60}\text{H}_{89}\text{NO}_{11}\text{P}^+$ 1030.6168; Found 1030.6180.

Phosphonium salt 3f: 195 mg, 39 % yield. Isolated as a white amorphous solid, a single spot by TLC. UV-active and stains green with PMA; ^1H NMR (400 MHz, CD_3CN) δ 5.82 (s, 1H), 5.56 (s, 1H), 4.34 (ddd, $J = 9.6, 7.4, 4.1$ Hz, 1H), 4.24 (s, 1H), 4.10 (t, $J = 5.9$ Hz, 2H), 4.04 (d, $J = 3.4$ Hz, 1H), 4.00 (d, $J = 1.8$ Hz, 1H), 3.98 (d, $J = 1.9$ Hz, 1H), 3.97–3.91 (m, 1H), 3.86–3.82 (m, 1H), 3.76 (dd, $J = 4.9, 3.4$ Hz, 1H), 3.65 (dd, $J = 9.9, 1.9$ Hz, 1H), 3.62–3.55 (m, 1H), 3.40–3.33 (m, 1H), 3.29 (s, 2H), 2.89 (dd, $J = 6.8, 3.0$ Hz, 1H), 2.46–0.69 (m, 78H) ppm; ^{13}C NMR (101 MHz, CD_3CN) δ 176.1, 108.5, 99.1, 86.8, 86.5, 84.7, 81.9, 76.4, 74.9, 69.8, 69.1, 67.1, 63.9, 58.5, 41.7, 40.0, 36.7, 36.6, 36.3, 35.6, 35.2, 34.7, 33.4, 33.3, 32.3, 30.5, 30.4, 30.3, 29.7, 28.4, 28.3, 27.8, 26.9, 24.8, 24.7, 24.5, 24.4, 23.9, 23.9, 19.4, 19.2, 18.9, 18.7, 16.5, 16.1, 14.6, 13.8, 13.6, 13.3, 11.9, 11.0, 8.1 ppm; ^{31}P NMR (122 MHz, CD_3CN) δ 34.9 ppm; HRMS (ESI^+) m/z : $[\text{M}]^+$ Calcd for $\text{C}_{52}\text{H}_{96}\text{O}_{11}\text{P}^+$ 927.6685; Found 927.6689.

4.4. Synthesis of 6-bromohexanoic ester of monensin A (compound 4)

MON (2.25 g, 3.35 mmol, 1.0 equiv.) was dissolved in toluene (60 mL) and the solution was heated to 90 °C. After 15 min, DBU (868 mg, 5.70 mmol, 1.7 equiv.) was added dropwise to the reaction mixture, and after another 20 min, 1,6-dibromohexane (2.45 g, 10.06 mmol, 3.0 equiv.) was added dropwise. After a few minutes, the color of the solution changed to brown. The resulting solution was stirred for the next 24 h. The reaction mixture was then concentrated on a rotary evaporator. Purification on silica gel using the CombiFlash system (0 %→50 % EtOAc/hexane) gave the pure ester **4** as a colorless oil. After twice co-evaporation to dryness with *n*-pentane, the product remained in an oily form (1.40 g, 50 % yield). The spectroscopic data were in agreement with previously published data [18].

4.5. Synthesis of triphenylphosphonium salt of monensin A with hexane-like linker (analog 5a)

1,6-dibromohexane (1.0 g, 4.10 mmol, 1.0 equiv.) was dissolved in CH_3CN (30 mL) and then triphenylphosphine (538 mg, 2.05 mmol, 0.5 equiv.) was added upon stirring. The solution was then refluxed for 72 h and subsequently concentrated on a rotary evaporator. The resulting oily residue was used without purification for the next step.

MON (200 mg, 0.30 mmol, 1 equiv.) was dissolved in toluene (20 mL) and the solution was heated to 90 °C. After 15 min, DBU (77 mg, 0.51 mmol, 1.7 equiv.) was added dropwise to the reaction mixture, and after another 20 min (6-bromohexyl)triphenylphosphonium bromide obtained in the previous step (452 mg, 0.90 mmol, 3.0 equiv.) was

added. The resulting solution was stirred for the next 24 h. The reaction mixture was then concentrated on a rotary evaporator. Purification on silica gel using the CombiFlash system (0 %→40 % acetone/ CHCl_3) gave the analog **5a** as a colorless oil. After twice co-evaporation to dryness with *n*-pentane, the oily product was completely converted into white amorphous solid.

Phosphonium salt 5a: 151 mg, 43 % yield. Isolated as a white amorphous solid, a single spot by TLC. UV-active and stains green with PMA; ^1H NMR (401 MHz, CD_3CN) δ 7.95–7.60 (m, 15H), 5.82 (s, 1H), 5.60 (s, 1H), 4.34 (ddd, $J = 9.6, 7.3, 4.1$ Hz, 1H), 4.10 (t, $J = 3.3$ Hz, 1H), 4.07–3.91 (m, 5H), 3.78–3.68 (m, 2H), 3.68–3.54 (m, 3H), 3.52–3.31 (m, 4H), 2.92–2.78 (m, 1H), 2.37 (s, 1H), 2.31–2.19 (m, 2H), 2.17–0.67 (m, 51H) ppm; ^{13}C NMR (101 MHz, CD_3CN) δ 176.3, 134.8, 134.7, 131.3, 131.2, 119.9, 119.1, 108.6, 99.3, 86.9, 86.6, 84.8, 82.2, 82.0, 76.5, 74.9, 69.9, 69.4, 67.3, 64.8, 58.7, 55.5, 41.7, 40.2, 37.1, 36.7, 36.5, 35.7, 35.3, 34.9, 33.6, 33.4, 32.4, 32.3, 30.7, 30.5, 29.9, 29.8, 29.0, 28.5, 27.0, 26.1, 23.1, 23.1, 23.0, 22.5, 16.6, 16.2, 14.7, 13.6, 11.8, 11.1, 8.3 ppm; ^{31}P NMR (122 MHz, CD_3CN) δ 25.3 ppm; HRMS (ESI^+) m/z : $[\text{M}]^+$ Calcd for $\text{C}_{60}\text{H}_{88}\text{O}_{11}\text{P}^+$ 1015.6059; Found 1015.6064.

4.6. General procedure for preparation of phosphonium salts of monensin A with hexane-like linker (analog 5b–5f)

Compound **4** (250 mg, 0.30 mmol, 1.0 equiv.) was dissolved in CH_3CN (30 mL) and the respective phosphine (0.90 mmol, 3.0 equiv.) was added upon stirring. The solution was then refluxed for 72 h. After this time, the reaction mixture was concentrated on a rotary evaporator. Purification on silica gel using the CombiFlash system (0 %→40 % acetone/ CHCl_3) gave the phosphonium salts of **MON** as colorless oils. After twice co-evaporation to dryness with *n*-pentane, the oily products were completely converted into white amorphous solids.

Phosphonium salt 5b: 51 mg, 15 % yield. Isolated as a white amorphous solid, a single spot by TLC. UV-active and stains green with PMA; ^1H NMR (401 MHz, CD_3CN) δ 7.70–7.46 (m, 11H), 7.20 (dd, $J = 9.0, 2.6$ Hz, 1H), 5.99–5.84 (m, 1H), 5.72–5.51 (m, 1H), 4.46–4.23 (m, 1H), 4.11–3.94 (m, 6H), 3.89 (s, 2H), 3.88–3.82 (m, 1H), 3.75 (dd, $J = 4.5, 2.6$ Hz, 1H), 3.69–3.63 (m, 2H), 3.60 (dd, $J = 10.0, 6.0$ Hz, 1H), 3.36 (dd, $J = 9.0, 3.3$ Hz, 1H), 2.86 (dd, $J = 6.8, 3.3$ Hz, 1H), 2.46 (s, 9H), 2.35–0.68 (m, 55H) ppm; ^{13}C NMR (101 MHz, CD_3CN) δ 176.1, 147.2, 147.2, 136.6, 136.5, 134.5, 134.4, 131.8, 131.6, 116.7, 115.8, 108.5, 99.2, 86.9, 86.5, 84.7, 82.1, 81.9, 76.4, 74.9, 69.8, 69.3, 67.3, 64.7, 58.6, 56.6, 41.7, 40.1, 36.9, 36.5, 36.3, 35.6, 35.2, 34.8, 33.5, 33.3, 32.3, 30.7, 30.5, 30.2, 29.7, 29.0, 28.3, 26.9, 26.1, 21.7, 21.7, 16.5, 16.1, 14.6, 13.5, 11.9, 10.9, 8.1 ppm; ^{31}P NMR (122 MHz, CD_3CN) δ 24.2 ppm; HRMS (ESI^+) m/z : $[\text{M}]^+$ Calcd for $\text{C}_{63}\text{H}_{94}\text{O}_{11}\text{P}^+$ 1057.6528; Found 1057.6527.

Phosphonium salt 5c: 121 mg, 34 % yield. Isolated as a white amorphous solid, a single spot by TLC. UV-active and stains green with PMA; ^1H NMR (600 MHz, CD_3CN) δ 7.67–7.60 (m, 6H), 7.22–7.18 (m, 6H), 5.87 (d, $J = 1.3$ Hz, 1H), 5.59 (dd, $J = 2.9, 1.9$ Hz, 1H), 4.37 (ddd, $J = 9.6, 7.2, 4.2$ Hz, 1H), 4.10–3.99 (m, 5H), 3.97 (dd, $J = 9.4, 1.9$ Hz, 1H), 3.90 (s, 9H), 3.85 (t, $J = 3.8$ Hz, 1H), 3.78–3.74 (m, 1H), 3.68–3.65 (m, 2H), 3.61 (dd, $J = 10.0, 5.9$ Hz, 1H), 3.50–3.47 (m, 1H), 3.37 (ddd, $J = 9.8, 4.3, 1.7$ Hz, 1H), 3.26–3.25 (m, 3H), 3.24–3.15 (m, 2H), 3.07 (qd, $J = 7.4, 5.1$ Hz, 1H), 2.86 (qd, $J = 6.8, 3.3$ Hz, 1H), 2.58 (s, 1H), 2.34–0.71 (m, 49H) ppm; ^{13}C NMR (151 MHz, CD_3CN) δ 176.2, 165.5, 165.5, 136.6, 136.5, 116.7, 116.7, 110.7, 110.1, 108.6, 99.2, 86.9, 86.5, 84.7, 82.1, 81.9, 79.2, 76.4, 74.9, 70.2, 69.8, 69.3, 67.3, 64.8, 58.6, 56.6, 56.4, 55.2, 41.7, 40.1, 36.9, 36.5, 36.3, 35.6, 35.2, 34.8, 33.5, 33.3, 32.3, 32.1, 30.6, 30.5, 30.4, 29.8, 29.7, 29.0, 28.3, 26.9, 26.2, 23.8, 23.5, 23.1, 23.0, 16.4, 16.1, 14.6, 13.6, 11.9, 11.0, 8.1 ppm; ^{31}P NMR (122 MHz, CD_3CN) δ 22.8 ppm; HRMS (ESI^+) m/z : $[\text{M}]^+$ Calcd for $\text{C}_{63}\text{H}_{94}\text{O}_{14}\text{P}^+$ 1105.6376; Found 1105.6390.

Phosphonium salt 5d: 85 mg, 24 % yield. Isolated as a white amorphous solid, a single spot by TLC. UV-active and stains green with PMA; ^1H NMR (400 MHz, CD_3CN) δ 7.82–7.76 (m, 2H), 7.55–7.50 (m, 1H),

7.42 (ddd, $J = 14.7, 7.8, 1.7$ Hz, 1H), 7.28–7.13 (m, 7H), 7.04–6.99 (m, 1H), 5.87 (d, $J = 1.5$ Hz, 1H), 5.61 (dd, $J = 3.3, 1.9$ Hz, 1H), 4.36 (ddd, $J = 9.6, 7.2, 4.1$ Hz, 1H), 4.04 (dd, $J = 8.4, 4.4$ Hz, 2H), 4.02–3.95 (m, 2H), 3.87 (t, $J = 3.6$ Hz, 1H), 3.79 (dt, $J = 6.4, 3.3$ Hz, 1H), 3.74 (dd, $J = 5.4, 3.1$ Hz, 1H), 3.72 (s, 9H), 3.62 (ddd, $J = 15.8, 9.8, 4.4$ Hz, 2H), 3.53–3.50 (m, 2H), 3.45 (s, 1H), 3.36 (ddd, $J = 9.8, 4.1, 1.7$ Hz, 1H), 3.23 (s, 2H), 3.15–3.05 (m, 2H), 2.83 (ddd, $J = 13.9, 6.9, 3.0$ Hz, 1H), 2.63 (s, 1H), 2.58 (s, 1H), 2.35–0.70 (m, 50H) ppm; ^{13}C NMR (101 MHz, CD_3CN) δ 176.1, 162.5, 162.5, 137.6, 137.6, 135.8, 135.7, 122.8, 122.7, 113.7, 113.6, 108.5, 107.6, 106.7, 99.1, 86.8, 86.5, 84.7, 82.0, 81.9, 79.2, 76.4, 74.9, 70.1, 69.7, 69.3, 67.2, 64.8, 58.4, 56.8, 56.4, 56.0, 55.2, 41.6, 40.0, 36.9, 36.6, 36.3, 35.5, 35.2, 34.7, 33.5, 33.3, 32.3, 30.9, 30.7, 30.4, 30.2, 29.8, 29.6, 29.0, 28.3, 26.9, 26.1, 16.4, 16.1, 14.6, 13.5, 11.7, 11.0, 8.1 ppm; ^{31}P NMR (122 MHz, CD_3CN) δ 26.6 ppm; HRMS (ESI⁺) m/z : [M]⁺ Calcd for $\text{C}_{63}\text{H}_{94}\text{O}_{14}\text{P}^+$ 1105.6376; Found 1105.6381.

Phosphonium salt 5e: 106 mg, 31 % yield. Isolated as a white amorphous solid, a single spot by TLC. UV-active and stains green with PMA; ^1H NMR (600 MHz, CD_3CN) δ 7.84–7.79 (m, 2H), 7.75–7.66 (m, 8H), 7.49–7.43 (m, 2H), 6.91–6.87 (m, 2H), 5.87 (s, 1H), 5.61 (s, 1H), 4.36 (ddd, $J = 9.6, 7.2, 4.1$ Hz, 1H), 4.10–3.98 (m, 5H), 3.97 (dd, $J = 9.4, 1.9$ Hz, 1H), 3.87 (t, $J = 3.5$ Hz, 1H), 3.76 (dd, $J = 5.1, 3.2$ Hz, 1H), 3.72–3.64 (m, 2H), 3.60 (dd, $J = 10.0, 5.9$ Hz, 1H), 3.51 (s, 1H), 3.45 (s, 1H), 3.37 (ddd, $J = 9.9, 4.2, 1.7$ Hz, 1H), 3.25–3.16 (m, 2H), 3.06 (s, 6H), 2.86 (qd, $J = 6.9, 3.1$ Hz, 1H), 2.63 (s, 2H), 2.58 (s, 3H), 2.33–0.68 (m, 48H) ppm; ^{13}C NMR (151 MHz, CD_3CN) δ 176.2, 155.1, 155.0, 135.8, 135.7, 135.4, 134.39, 134.38, 134.33, 134.32, 131.0, 130.9, 113.34, 113.25, 108.6, 99.2, 86.9, 86.5, 84.7, 82.0, 81.9, 76.4, 74.9, 70.2, 69.9, 69.8, 69.4, 67.3, 64.8, 58.5, 56.5, 55.2, 41.6, 40.1, 36.9, 36.5, 36.3, 35.6, 35.2, 34.8, 33.5, 33.3, 32.3, 32.1, 30.7, 30.6, 30.5, 29.8, 29.7, 29.0, 28.3, 26.9, 26.1, 23.1, 16.5, 16.1, 14.6, 13.5, 11.8, 11.0, 8.1 ppm; ^{31}P NMR (122 MHz, CD_3CN) δ 23.6 ppm; HRMS (ESI⁺) m/z : [M]⁺ Calcd for $\text{C}_{62}\text{H}_{93}\text{NO}_{11}\text{P}^+$ 1058.6481; Found 1058.6480.

Phosphonium salt 5f: 71 mg, 23 % yield. Isolated as a white amorphous solid, a single spot by TLC. UV-active and stains green with PMA; ^1H NMR (401 MHz, CD_3CN) δ 5.85 (s, 1H), 5.64 (s, 1H), 4.34 (t, $J = 9.6$ Hz, 1H), 4.12–3.91 (m, 8H), 3.83 (s, 1H), 3.76 (s, 1H), 3.69–3.57 (m, 3H), 3.37 (dd, $J = 10.2, 3.0$ Hz, 1H), 2.86 (s, 1H), 2.39–0.66 (m, 82H) ppm; ^{13}C NMR (101 MHz, CD_3CN) δ 176.2, 108.5, 99.1, 86.9, 86.5, 84.8, 82.2, 76.5, 69.9, 69.2, 67.2, 64.9, 58.6, 41.7, 40.0, 37.0, 36.7, 36.3, 35.2, 34.8, 33.4, 30.9, 30.7, 29.7, 28.9, 25.9, 24.5, 24.37, 23.92, 23.9, 21.9, 21.8, 19.5, 19.2, 19.1, 19.0, 18.74, 18.66, 16.46, 13.8, 13.5, 11.9, 11.0, 8.1 ppm; ^{31}P NMR (122 MHz, CD_3CN) δ 34.9 ppm; HRMS (ESI⁺) m/z : [M]⁺ Calcd for $\text{C}_{54}\text{H}_{100}\text{O}_{11}\text{P}^+$ 955.6998; Found 955.7017.

4.7. Synthesis of benzyl ester of monensin A (compound 6)

MON (0.5 g, 0.75 mmol, 1.0 equiv.) was dissolved in toluene (20 mL) and the solution was heated to 90 °C. After 15 min, DBU (193 mg, 1.27 mmol, 1.7 equiv.) was added dropwise to the reaction mixture, and after another 20 min, benzyl bromide (382 mg, 2.24 mmol, 3.0 equiv.) was added dropwise. After a few minutes, the color of the solution changed to brown. The resulting solution was stirred for the next 24 h. The reaction mixture was then concentrated on a rotary evaporator *in vacuo*. Purification on silica gel using the CombiFlash system (0 %→50 % EtOAc/hexane) gave the pure ester **6** as a colorless oil. After twice co-evaporation to dryness with *n*-pentane, the oily product was completely converted into white amorphous solid (438 mg, 77 % yield). The spectroscopic data were in agreement with previously published data [18].

4.8. In vitro biological studies

4.8.1. Culture cell lines

The study was conducted on various cell lines, including human primary (SW480) and metastatic (SW620) colon cancer, human

metastatic prostate cancer (PC3), human breast cancer (MDA-MB-231), human lung cancer (A549), human immortal keratinocytes (HaCaT), and Chinese hamster lung fibroblasts (V79). All cell lines, obtained from the repository of the Medical University of Warsaw, were cultured in the recommended medium supplemented with 10 % fetal bovine serum, penicillin (100 U/mL), and streptomycin (100 µg/L) at 37 °C with 5 % CO_2 . Once the cells reached 80 % confluence, they were harvested using 0.25 % trypsin (Gibco Life Technologies), seeded into 96-, 12-, and 6-well plates, and incubated for 24 h at 37 °C with 5 % CO_2 for optimal attachment before being used in further assays.

4.8.2. MTT assay

The cytotoxic activity of monensin (**MON**) and its derivatives was assessed by MTT assay. The cells were seeded (5×10^3 cells per well) in 96-well plates, and after 24 h of incubation, the cells were treated with the studied compounds at concentrations ranging from 0.5 to 40 µM. After 72 h of incubation at 37 °C/5 % CO_2 , the culture medium was removed and MTT solution (0.5 mg/mL) was added to each well. Next, the cells were incubated for additional 4 h at 37 °C/5 % CO_2 . The developed formazan crystals were dissolved in DMSO and isopropanol mixture (1:1, v/v). The optical density of the solution was measured at a wavelength of 570 nm using a Multiscan Go spectrophotometer (ThermoScientific). Cell viability was assessed by calculating the percentage of MTT reduction in treated cells compared with that in untreated control cells. The relative MTT level was determined as a percentage using formula $[\text{A}]/[\text{B}] \times 100$, where [A] represents the absorbance of the tested samples and [B] stands for the absorbance of the controls. The IC_{50} values were determined using GraphPad Prism 8.0.1 software (GraphPad Software).

4.8.3. Cell cycle assay

A549 and MDA-MB-231 cells (1×10^5 cells per well) were seeded in 6-well plates and treated with the studied compounds at their IC_{50} concentrations for 24 h. Following treatment, both adherent and detached cells were collected and centrifuged at $450 \times g$ for 5 min at 4 °C. The cells were then washed twice with PBS and fixed overnight in cold 70 % ethanol at 4 °C. Before analysis, the fixed cells were centrifuged at $800 \times g$ for 5 min at 4 °C and washed again with PBS. The cells were then incubated with RNase (100 µg/mL) and stained with propidium iodide (PI, 50 µg/mL) at 37 °C for 30 min in the dark. After staining, 200 µL of PBS was added to each sample. The cell cycle stages (sub-G1, G0/G1, S, and G2/M phases) were analyzed using a flow cytometer (Becton Dickinson FACS Verse).

4.8.4. Mitochondrial activity

Cells (5×10^4 per well) were seeded in 12-well plates, treated with **MON** and selected derivatives at their IC_{50} concentrations, and incubated for 48 h at 37 °C with 5 % CO_2 . After incubation, both suspended and adherent cells were collected, centrifuged at $800 \times g$ for 5 min at 4 °C, washed twice with PBS, and stained with JC-10 (Abcam), MitoTracker Red CMXRos, and MitoTracker Green FM dyes (Invitrogen), following the manufacturers' protocols. Flow cytometry analysis (Becton Dickinson FACS Verse) was performed, where JC-10 aggregates (red fluorescence) were observed in the mitochondria during potential-dependent aggregation, while JC-10 monomers (green fluorescence) increased in the cytosol after mitochondrial membrane depolarization. MitoTracker Green FM binds to the mitochondrial membrane, indicating mitochondrial mass, and MitoTracker Red CMXRos localizes to the matrix of functional mitochondria, reflecting an intact mitochondrial membrane potential.

4.8.5. Annexin V-FITC/PI binding assay

A549 and MDA-MB-231 cells (5×10^4 cells per well) were seeded in 12-well plates and treated with **MON** and its selected derivatives (**3a**, **3f**, **6**) at their IC_{50} for 72 h. After treatment, both adherent and detached cells were collected, centrifuged at $800 \times g$ for 5 min at 4 °C, and washed

twice with cold PBS. The cells were then labeled with Annexin V-FITC and propidium iodide (PI) following the manufacturer's protocol (BD Biosciences Pharmingen). Stained cells were analyzed by flow cytometry (Becton Dickinson FACS Verse) to identify early apoptotic cells (Annexin V+/PI-) and late apoptotic or necrotic cells (Annexin V+/PI+).

4.8.6. ROS detection assay

A549 and MDA-MB-231 cells (5×10^4 cells per well) were seeded into black 96-well plates and treated with MON and its derivatives at their respective IC₅₀ concentrations. Following the treatment, the cells were incubated for 6 h at 37 °C with 5 % CO₂. Intracellular reactive oxygen species (ROS) levels were quantified using the CellROX™ Green Reagent (Invitrogen), following the protocol provided by the manufacturer. This cell-permeant probe remained weakly fluorescent in its reduced state and exhibited bright, photostable green fluorescence upon oxidation with ROS and subsequent interaction with DNA.

To validate the assay, H₂O₂ (1.5 mM) was used as a positive control to ensure robust ROS induction. The fluorescence intensity, indicative of ROS levels, was measured using a BioTek Synergy Microplate Spectrofluorometer (BioTek Instruments).

4.9. Biophysical studies

4.9.1. Cell culture

Oxygraph-2K experiments were performed on adenocarcinomic human alveolar basal epithelial cells (A549, Merck, Darmstadt, Germany). The cells were cultured on T75 flasks (Googlab™) in Dulbecco Minimal Essential Medium (DMEM; Merck, Darmstadt, Germany) supplemented with 10 % fetal bovine serum (FBS; Gibco, Thermo Fisher Scientific, Waltham, MA, USA) and antibiotics – 100 U/mL penicillin and 100 mg/mL streptomycin (Merck, Darmstadt, Germany). The cells were maintained in a humidified 5 % CO₂ atmosphere at 37 °C and reseeded when they reached 90 % confluence.

4.9.2. High-resolution respirometry

High-resolution respirometry was performed using an Oxygraph-2K system (Oroboros Instruments, Innsbruck, Austria) according to the commonly used method [35]. Briefly, A549 cells were harvested, centrifuged, and resuspended in starved DMEM (1 % FBS) in 1×10^6 cells/cm³. Cells were added to the respiratory chambers to measure basal respiration. MON and its derivatives in the concentration of 0.1, 0.3, 1, 3, and 10 μM were added to chambers after stabilization of the respiration. The maximum uncoupled electron transfer system (ETS) was measured using carbonyl cyanide-p-trifluoromethoxyphenylhydrazone (FCCP; 1 μM). The data are reported as mean values ± SD (SD, standard deviation).

4.9.3. Black lipid membrane technique (BLM)

Asolecetin dissolved in *n*-decane at a final concentration of 25 mg/mL was used as a model biological membrane and was applied using a polyethylene brush to the 250 μm diameter opening of the Teflon cup to separate the two chambers (*cis/trans*) [36,37]. To improve the lipid bilayer's stability, the aperture's outline was coated with a lipid solution and N₂-dried before bilayer formation. Overall, 1 mL of the solutions containing 50/150 mM NaCl (*cis/trans*) and 10 mM HEPES at pH = 7.2 were added to the measurement chambers and stirred using magnetic stirrers. Silver-chloride (Ag/AgCl) electrodes were introduced into the chambers and connected to the BLM-120 amplifier (Bio-Logic, Seyssinet-Pariset, France). The PowerLab 2/25 (ADInstruments, Sydney, Australia) converter processed the electric signal, recorded using LabChart5 and analyzed in Clampfit 8. The experiments were performed in Faraday's cage to prevent external electromagnetic interferences. All measurements were carried out at room temperature (25 °C). MON and the studied compounds were added to *trans* side chamber in the concentration of 0.1, 0.3, 1, 3, and 10 μM.

The bilayer formation and thinning were monitored by the

capacitance measurements and optical observations. The final accepted capacitance values ranged from 110 pF to 180 pF. Electrical connections were made by Ag/AgCl electrodes and agar salt bridges (3 M KCl) to minimize the liquid junction potentials. Voltage was applied to the *cis* compartment and the *trans* compartment was grounded.

The single-channel data were filtered at 500 Hz. The current was digitized at a sampling rate of 100 kHz. The single-channel currents were recorded at different voltages in steps of 20 mV. The data are reported as mean value ± SD (SD, standard deviation).

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Michał Sulik: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Project administration, Methodology, Investigation, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Marta Jędrzejczyk:** Investigation, **Magdalena Mielczarek-Put:** Writing – original draft, Visualization, Methodology, Investigation, Data curation. **Gwan Yong Lim:** Investigation. **Małgorzata Podsiad:** Investigation. **Jakub Hoser:** Writing – original draft, Visualization, Methodology, Investigation, Data curation. **Piotr Bednarczyk:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Validation, Methodology, Conceptualization. **Marta Struga:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Validation, Supervision, Conceptualization. **Adam Huczyński:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Validation, Supervision, Methodology, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ejmc.2025.100275>.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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